

Reply to “A 1d Up Approach to Conformal Geometric Algebra: Applications in Line Fitting and Quantum Mechanics”

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In a recent paper — published in *Advances in Applied Clifford Algebras* — a partial critique of the introductory Clifford-algebraic sections of my paper entitled ‘Quantum correlations are weaved by the spinors of the Euclidean primitives’ is presented. The geometrical framework presented in the original paper, based on an interplay between the 3- and 7-spheres, circumvents Bell’s theorem and allows a locally causal underpinning of quantum correlations, without requiring superdeterminism or backward causation. In the present paper I provide a point-by-point response to the said critique and demonstrate that none of the claims made in it are valid objections to the 7-sphere framework.

I. INTRODUCTION

In physics, sometimes a mathematical construction is obfuscated rather than enlightened by its misplaced criticism, and a recent critique [1] of the introductory parts of the construction I have presented in Ref. [2] is no exception. Let me therefore begin by summarizing my construction as clearly as possible before responding to the criticism in [1].

The proof of the celebrated theorem of Bell relies on strong correlations predicted by entangled quantum states, such as the singlet state [3]. The claim of the theorem is that no local and realistic theory of the kind espoused by Einstein can reproduce all of the statistical predictions of quantum mechanics, especially those that depend on quantum entanglement. But in a number of publications I have argued that the strong correlations observed in Nature have little to do with quantum entanglement *per se*. I argue they are local and realistic correlations among the limiting scalar points of an octonion-like 7-sphere [2], which is an algebraic representation space of a quaternionic 3-sphere [5]:

$$S^3 := \left\{ \mathbf{q}(\psi, \mathbf{r}) := \exp \left[\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r}) \frac{\psi}{2} \right] \mid \|\mathbf{q}(\psi, \mathbf{r})\|^2 = 1 \right\}, \quad (\text{R.1})$$

where $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r})$ is a bivector (or pure quaternion) rotating about $\mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ with the rotation angle ψ in the range $0 \leq \psi < 4\pi$. Thus S^3 is the set of unit quaternions [5]. Throughout this paper the notations and conventions of Geometric Algebra are followed [6]. Now, in the Bell-test experiments [7][8], physical space is customarily modeled as \mathbb{R}^3 and “vector algebra” is implicitly employed in all analyses and calculations. I argue, however, that we must model physical space as S^3 defined above, instead of \mathbb{R}^3 , and use Geometric Algebra to do so. This amounts to hypothesizing that we live in a quaternionic 3-sphere [5][9]. It is then possible to understand the strong correlations observed in the Bell-test experiments as local and realistic correlations among the limiting scalar points of such a 3-sphere [5][9]. This is by no means an *ad hoc* hypothesis, because S^3 happens to be the spatial part of one of the well known cosmological solutions of Einstein’s field equations of general relativity, representing a closed Universe with positive curvature [5][9].

For understanding more general quantum correlations, however, the quaternionic 3-sphere by itself is not sufficient. What is needed is an algebraic representation space of the 3-sphere defined in (R.1). And this is where a vector space \mathcal{K}^λ corresponding to the eight-dimensional even sub-algebra of the $2^4 = 16$ -dimensional Clifford algebra $Cl_{4,0}$ comes to rescue. This space provides a conformal counterpart of the algebra $Cl_{3,0}$ and can be restricted to a unit 7-sphere:

$$\mathcal{K}^\lambda \supset S^7 := \left\{ \mathbb{Q}_z := \mathbf{q}_r + \mathbf{q}_d \varepsilon \mid \|\mathbb{Q}_z\| = 1 \text{ and } \mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0 \right\}, \quad (\text{R.2})$$

where $\lambda = \pm 1$ specifies the orientation or handedness of \mathcal{K}^λ and S^7 , $\varepsilon = -\lambda I_3 \mathbf{e}_\infty$, $I_3 = \mathbf{e}_x \wedge \mathbf{e}_y \wedge \mathbf{e}_z$, $\varepsilon^2 = \mathbf{e}_\infty^2 = +1$,

$$\mathbf{q}_r = q_0 + q_1 \lambda \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y + q_2 \lambda \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_x + q_3 \lambda \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z, \text{ and } \mathbf{q}_d = -q_7 + q_6 \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y + q_5 \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_x + q_4 \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z, \quad (\text{R.3})$$

so that

$$\mathcal{K}^\lambda \ni \mathbb{Q}_z = q_0 + q_1 \lambda \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y + q_2 \lambda \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_x + q_3 \lambda \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z + q_4 \lambda \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_\infty + q_5 \lambda \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_\infty + q_6 \lambda \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_\infty + q_7 \lambda I_3 \mathbf{e}_\infty. \quad (\text{R.4})$$

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Here all quaternions \mathbf{q}_r and \mathbf{q}_d in (R.5) satisfy the normalization condition $\mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0$ ensuring the relation

$$\|\mathbb{Q}_{z1} \mathbb{Q}_{z2}\| = \|\mathbb{Q}_{z1}\| \|\mathbb{Q}_{z2}\|, \quad (\text{R.5})$$

which is necessary for the construction of S^7 defined in (R.2) as an algebraic representation space of S^3 defined in (R.1). It proves that the finite-dimensional algebra \mathcal{K}^λ over the reals can be equipped with a positive definite quadratic form \mathcal{Q} (the square of the norm) such that $\mathcal{Q}(XY) = \mathcal{Q}(X) \mathcal{Q}(Y)$ for all X and Y in \mathcal{K}^λ . Consequently, a product XY would vanish if and only if X or Y vanishes. In other words, \mathcal{K}^λ , equipped with \mathcal{Q} , is a division algebra. The proof of the norm relation (R.5) is given in Section 2.5 of Ref. [2], and it is repeated in more detail in Ref. [10]. Thus, unlike the non-associative octonionic algebra, the 7-sphere we have constructed corresponds to an *associative* (but of course non-commutative) algebra. This leads to the main theorem presented in Section 3.2 of Ref. [2]: *Every quantum mechanical correlation can be understood as a classical, local, realistic, and deterministic correlation among a set of points of the 7-sphere defined in Eq. (R.2)*. With this background, I now proceed to respond to the critique in [1].

II. POINT-BY-POINT RESPONSE TO THE CRITICISM

The main focus of the criticism in [1] is the construction of the 7-sphere defined in (R.2), based on the norm relation (R.5). For convenience, in what follows I will first reproduce each comment in [1] in a quotation format, and then respond to it point-by-point. All quotations are from the critique published in *Advances in Applied Clifford Algebras* [1].

Critique:

Abstract: ... we consider a further perhaps surprising application of the 1d up approach, which is to the context of a recent paper by Joy Christian published by the Royal Society, which has made strong claims about Bell's Theorem in quantum mechanics, and its relation to the sphere S^7 and the exceptional group E_8 , and proposed a new *associative* version of the division algebra normally thought to require the octonians. We show that what is being discussed by Christian is mathematically the same as our 1d up approach to 3d geometry, but that after the removal of some incorrect mathematical assertions, the results he proves in the first part of the paper, and bases the application to Bell's Theorem on, amount to no more than the statement that the combination of two rotors from the Clifford Algebra $Cl(4,0)$ is also a rotor.

Section 3: In 2018, a paper was published in a Royal Society journal by Christian [2], which was discussed during the AGACSE 2018 meeting in Campinas, Brazil. This paper is called 'Quantum correlations are weaved by the spinors of the Euclidean primitives', and makes some strong claims about Bell's Theorem in quantum mechanics, and its relation to the sphere S^7 and the exceptional group E_8 . Perhaps most startling mathematically, as against physically, however, is the author's claim to have discovered a new *associative* version of the normed division algebra hitherto represented by the octonians. Joy Christian uses Geometric Algebra in his work, and claims that his new physical results in Quantum Mechanics stem from the employment of GA, and the additional geometrical elements of reality which it can introduce in addition to the usual complex numbers used in Quantum Mechanics. In previous papers he has mainly considered the ordinary GA, but in the 2018 Royal Society paper he says he is considering the 'Conformal Geometric Algebra' and explicitly links the 'Euclidean primitives' of CGA with his statements about Bell's Theorem.

Response: I partially agree with the above comments. There are indeed some similarities between the so-called "1d up approach to Conformal Geometric Algebra" and what is discussed in the introductory sections of my paper [2]. However, as we shall see in detail below, there are no "incorrect mathematical assertions" in my paper. The assertions made in my paper are all perfectly meaningful within the context of the geometrical framework presented in the paper. Moreover, there is a subtle difference between the result proved in Subsection 2.5 of my paper and the statement that the combination of two rotors from the Clifford Algebra $Cl(4,0)$ is also a rotor, as I have also explained in Ref. [10].

It is also important to note from the outset that Bell's theorem is not a theorem "in" quantum mechanics itself. And it is not a theorem in the mathematical sense. It is a physical argument based on a number of questionable assumptions, which have been questioned throughout the history of the "theorem." In the Introduction and Section 4.2 of my paper [2] I have explained the faulty assumptions in Bell's argument in considerable detail. As I have further explained in [11], the proof of Bell's theorem is circular. It presumes, in a different guise, what it intends to prove.

Critique: Christian’s work has repeatedly been criticised mathematically, but he has several times stated that no one well-versed in Geometric Algebra has explicitly criticised his mathematics in print, and that this suggests his critics simply do not understand the GA in his work, not that his mathematics is wrong.

Response: It is correct that there have been prior critiques of my work on Bell’s theorem. For example, in an unpublished preprint [12] there is an attempt to criticize an earlier version of the local-realistic model that I have now published in [5]. This critique, however, contains quite a few elementary mathematical and conceptual mistakes, as I have demonstrated in [13]. For example, the abstract of the first version of this preprint refers to the quantity $-\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b}$ as a “bivector.” And even after my detailed explanations of the difference between a cross product and a wedge product, and the difference between a bivector and a multivector within Geometric Algebra, all subsequent versions of this preprint continue the mistake of referring to the multivector $-\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{a} \wedge \mathbf{b}$ as a “bivector”, leading to more serious mistakes later on in the critique. I have systematically corrected these mistakes in my responses [13], [14], and [15].

Furthermore, in the latest version of [12] (version 7), further elementary mistakes are added. For example, in the beginning of an argument it is written: “Take any unit bivector v . It satisfies $v^2 = 1$ hence $v^2 - 1 = (v - 1)(v + 1) = 0$.” But any unit bivector squares to -1 , not $+1$. Consequently, this mistake reduces the entire argument to absurdity.

In a second paper [16] my proposed experiment to test the relevance of Bell’s theorem in a macroscopic setting [17] is criticised. Unfortunately, this critique too contains surprisingly elementary mathematical and conceptual mistakes. For example, in the very equation of mine that it claims to be criticizing (namely, the standard definition of the bivector subalgebra [6]), the critique forgets to sum over the bivector-index, arriving at a rather strange conclusion. What is more, the Bell-CHSH correlator is also calculated incorrectly in [16], by summing over spin detections of physically incompatible experiments. I have explained these and other mistakes in my response [15] and analysis [18].

Critique: Stimulated by the discussion at the AGACSE meeting, I have looked at the first sections of the Royal Society paper, and found that (a), quite surprisingly, the CGA he is using is in fact a version of the 1d-up approach I have been suggesting, and (b) it is possible to find where the mathematical mistakes lie which lead to his conclusions concerning a new associative division algebra. Thus this current contribution on the 1d-up approach, provides an opportunity to record these comments as regards the mathematics that he appears to be using, and hopefully warn about the mistakes involved.

Response: As I have demonstrated in Ref. [10] in considerable detail and again demonstrate below, there are no mathematical mistakes in my construction of associative normed division algebra from the even sub-algebra of $Cl_{4,0}$.

Critique: However, it is very necessary to stress that this in no way is meant to transfer through to being a comment about what Christian is saying as regards Bell’s Theorem. At a certain level there is certainly an interest in taking a 1d-up approach to quantum mechanics and electromagnetism, as discussed briefly by myself in a relativistic context in [7], but this area lies outside the discussion we will attempt here. In particular the comments here only relate to Sections 1 and 2 of the Christian paper, before the main work on Bell’s Theorem begins. Of course the mathematical problems and misstatements in this first part of the paper would certainly need to be remedied before being able to approach the second part properly, hence it seems of value to record the objections here. (Note several of the points made here have been made independently by Richard D. Gill and others in the discussion thread attached to the Royal Society paper: https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/full/10.1098/rsos.180526#disqus_thread, but what may be useful here is decoding what Christian is claiming in terms of the unexpected link with the 1d-up approach, and also making a statement on these issues from a practicing GA person.

Response: As I demonstrate below, there are no mathematical problems and misstatements in any part of my paper requiring remedy. The online thread that is quoted in the critique also contains my detailed responses to each criticism.

Critique:

Subsection 3.1. Initial Problems

(Note most equation numbers from now on relate to those in the paper [2], and we will say explicitly if we mean an equation in the current contribution.)

The first maths problem comes in Christian’s equation (2.20), which says

$$\mathbf{e}_\infty^2 = 0 \tag{3.1}$$

FIG. 1: One-point compactification of the Euclidean space \mathbb{E}^3 by means of a stereographic projection onto $S^3 \in \mathbb{R}^4$.

and then that

Such a vector that is orthogonal to itself is called a null vector in Conformal Geometric Algebra [18]. It is introduced to represent both finite points in space as well as points at infinity [19]. As points thus defined are null-dimensional or dimensionless, addition of \mathbf{e}_∞ into the algebraic structure of \mathbb{E}^3 does not alter the latter's dimensions but only its pointset topology, rendering it diffeomorphic to a closed, compact, simply connected 3-sphere . . .

I do not see how it can be thought introducing \mathbf{e}_∞ into the algebraic structure of \mathbb{E}^3 does not alter its dimensions. Also, since null vectors are described as representing both finite points as well as points at infinity, which is true in the CGA, the logic of this paragraph seems to be that since these points are null-dimensional or dimensionless then addition of any of them into \mathbb{E}^3 could go ahead and \mathbb{E}^3 would only be changed in topology.

Response: There is no “maths problem” or even a conceptual problem here. What is stated in the quoted paragraph is quite easy to understand, unless one has missed what has been presented in the Subsection 2.1 entitled “One-point compactification of the three-dimensional Euclidean Space.” In Eq. (2.15) of that subsection the null vector \mathbf{e}_∞ is introduced, which represents a single dimensionless point at infinity in the physical space \mathbb{E}^3 :

$$S^3 = \mathbb{E}^3 \cup \{\mathbf{e}_\infty\}. \quad (2.15)$$

This is an example of the well known one-point or Alexandroff compactification [19]. Here \mathbf{e}_∞ is introduced in Subsection 2.1 after considerable discussion, providing explicit construction in equations (2.12) to (2.14), and with the help of Figures 2 and 3 (I have reproduced Figure 2 of Ref. [2] as Fig. 1 here for convenience). As we can see from Figure 2, \mathbf{e}_∞ is clearly a null vector [20] within the compactified physical space S^3 , but a unit vector within the space \mathbb{R}^4 that embeds S^3 . Thus the logic of the quoted paragraph is that the addition of the null vector \mathbf{e}_∞ to \mathbb{E}^3 in the manner shown in Figure 2 transforms \mathbb{E}^3 into S^3 , as stated in equation (2.15). Moreover, it is clear that the spaces \mathbb{E}^3 and S^3 are both *three*-dimensional and differ only by a single dimensionless point, whereas the space \mathbb{R}^4 that embeds the space S^3 is four-dimensional [2]. Thus the addition of the null vector \mathbf{e}_∞ to \mathbb{E}^3 compactifies it into S^3 , thereby changing its topology from \mathbb{R}^3 to S^3 , but retaining the algebraic structure of the space \mathbb{E}^3 . Unfortunately, the critique seems to have overlooked the discussion in Subsection 2.1 and jumped straight to the Subsection 2.2 containing Eq. (2.20).

Critique: The main problem with (2.20), however, is that it is shortly contradicted by (2.32), which says that $\mathbf{e}_\infty^2 = 1$. To give the full context at this point, it is said:

The three-dimensional physical space—i.e. the compact 3-sphere we discussed above—can now be viewed as embedded in the four-dimensional ambient space, \mathbb{R}^4 , as depicted in Fig. 2. In this higher dimensional space, \mathbf{e}_∞ is then a unit vector,

$$\|\mathbf{e}_\infty\|^2 = \mathbf{e}_\infty \cdot \mathbf{e}_\infty = 1 \iff \mathbf{e}_\infty^2 = 1,$$

and the corresponding algebraic representation space (2.31) is nothing but the eight-dimensional even sub-algebra of the $2^4 = 16$ -dimensional Clifford algebra $Cl_{4,0}$. Thus a one-dimensional subspace—represented by the unit vector \mathbf{e}_∞ in the ambient space \mathbb{R}^4 —represents a null-dimensional space—i.e., the infinite point of \mathbb{E}^3 —in the physical space S^3 .

Again this is very difficult to understand mathematically, as anything which tries to reconcile $e_\infty^2 = 0$ in 3d, with the same object squaring to +1 when interpreted as living in 4d, is bound to be.

Response: There is nothing incomprehensible or unorthodox here. As I noted in my previous response, there is no contradiction between equations (2.20) and (2.32). These equations would have been contradictory if they had been claimed to be meaningful within the same mathematical space. But that is not the case. It is evident from the one-point compactification illustrated in Figure 2 that \mathbf{e}_∞ is a null vector within S^3 whereas a unit vector within its embedding space \mathbb{R}^4 . The purpose of the one-point compactification of the space \mathbb{E}^3 is physical, as discussed in Subsection 2.1. Later, the calculations of the strong correlations are carried out entirely using the algebra given in the multiplication table 1 on page 8 of the paper, which involves only $e_\infty^2 = 1$. Thus no difficulty arises in understanding the meaning of the vector e_∞ for the actual calculations in [2]. The geometrical framework constructed in the paper is discussed in considerable detail in Section 2, starting with explaining the necessity of compactifying the physical space \mathbb{E}^3 by adding a single point to it at infinity, in order to better understand the origins and strengths of quantum correlations. Compactifying the physical space in this manner transforms it into S^3 . While it is well known that the algebraic representation space of \mathbb{E}^3 is the Clifford algebra $Cl_{3,0}$, one of the tasks in the paper is to find the algebraic representation space of the compactified physical space S^3 defined in (2.16). After some effort in Section 2, this is found to be S^7 defined in Eq. (2.60), whose eight-dimensional embedding space happens to be the even subalgebra of $Cl_{4,0}$.

Critique: The next problem is Eq. (2.25), which concerns the reversion properties of the pseudoscalar I_c , which is introduced in Eq. (2.24) as

$$I_c = \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_\infty. \quad (3.2)$$

The multiplication properties given for the 8 quantities

$$\{ 1, \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y, \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z, \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_\infty, I_c \}$$

in Table 1, tell us unambiguously that these quantities correspond to the 8 elements of the even subalgebra of $Cl_{4,0}$, with I_c being the pseudoscalar for this space. This is not different from what Christian says, but he says in Eq. (2.25) that I_c reverses to minus itself, i.e. (to quote)

$$I_c^\dagger = I_3^\dagger \mathbf{e}_\infty = -I_3 \mathbf{e}_\infty = -I_c. \quad (3.3)$$

(Note there appears to be no dispute over the dagger operation being ‘reversion’, and we will denote it with the usual tilde from now on.)

But this equation is *wrong*. We have

$$\tilde{I}_c = \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_x = -\mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_\infty = -\mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_\infty = \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_\infty = I_c \quad (3.4)$$

i.e. it reverses to *plus* itself. Thus if Christian’s Eq. (2.25) is used anywhere, it will lead to error.

Response: To begin with, Eq. (2.25) is not used anywhere in the rest of the paper. It is an *intermediate* step, eventually leading to the multiplication table 1 provided on page 8. As stated in the critique, this table does tabulate the multiplication properties given for the 8 quantities $\{ 1, \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y, \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z, \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_\infty, I_3 \mathbf{e}_\infty \}$, and does tell us unambiguously that these quantities correspond to the 8 elements of the even subalgebra of $Cl_{4,0}$. However, the critique has overlooked the context within which equation (2.25) appears in the paper. In particular, once again what has been discussed in Subsection 2.1 prior to the appearance of equation (2.25), and what has been discussed just before equation (2.25) appears to be overlooked. At that stage in the paper we have not yet arrived at the even subalgebra of $Cl_{4,0}$ or Table 1. We are still working within the algebra $Cl_{3,0}$ defined in the equation (2.10). In this algebra the volume form is $I_3 = \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z$, and its reverse is $I_3^\dagger = \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_x$. Now, as stated in the paper: “this volume form is open and has the topology of \mathbb{R}^3 . But we can now close it with the null vector \mathbf{e}_∞ .” In fact, both $I_3 = \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z$ and its reverse $I_3^\dagger = \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_x$ are open and have to be closed with the null vector \mathbf{e}_∞ in the light of the discussion in

Subsection 2.1. There are two important points that have been overlooked: First, both $I_3 = \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z$ and $I_3^\dagger = \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_x$ are volume elements within the same space \mathbb{E}^3 . If one is deemed right-handed, then the other one is left-handed, and if one is deemed outside-in, then the other one is inside-out. But the important point is that both of them are volume elements within the same space. Secondly, both of them must be closed with the same point — *i.e.*, the same null vector \mathbf{e}_∞ — added at infinity, as depicted in Figure 2. The resulting closed volume forms are therefore $I_3 \mathbf{e}_\infty$ and $I_3^\dagger \mathbf{e}_\infty = -I_3 \mathbf{e}_\infty$. This is the origin of the minus sign in the Eq. (2.25) of the paper that the critique claims to be wrong.

But, as noted above, this equation is not used anywhere else in the paper because it is an intermediate step towards arriving at the multiplication table 1 on page 8. The minus sign in equation (2.25) becomes inconsequential as we pass through the discussion in Subsection 2.3 for this goal, since we have left the orientation of the space \mathcal{K}^λ unspecified.

Critique: The next problem is with Eqs. (2.33) and (2.34), which read

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{K}^+ &= \text{span}\{1, \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y, \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z, \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_\infty, \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_\infty, I_c\} \\ \mathcal{K}^- &= \text{span}\{1, -\mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y, -\mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_x, -\mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z, -\mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_\infty, -\mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_\infty, -\mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_\infty, -I_c\}\end{aligned}\quad (3.5)$$

It seems to be important to Christian's later purposes that \mathcal{K}^+ and \mathcal{K}^- are different, but as spans of objects which differ just by scalar factors from the same objects in the other set, they are mathematically identical. Presumably something different is meant from what is actually written at this point, but this would have to be explained, using some concrete definitions, before the differences between one \mathcal{K}^+ and \mathcal{K}^- could be used later in the paper.

Response: Nowhere in [2] it is stated that \mathcal{K}^+ and \mathcal{K}^- represent two different algebras. What is stated in Subsection 2.3 of [2] is that the vector spaces \mathcal{K}^+ and \mathcal{K}^- differ in their orientations λ , with $\lambda = +$ or $-$. If one of the vector spaces (say \mathcal{K}^+) is deemed right-handed, then the other one (\mathcal{K}^-) is left-handed, and vice versa [21]. Thus, the vector spaces \mathcal{K}^+ and \mathcal{K}^- are mathematically *not* identical. An entire subsection, Subsection 2.3, is devoted in [2] to explain and stress the significance of this elementary fact, with the definition of orientation given on page 7 of [2]:

Definition of Orientation: An orientation of a finite dimensional vector space \mathcal{V}_n is an equivalence class of ordered basis, say $\{b_1, \dots, b_n\}$, which determines the same orientation of \mathcal{V}_n as the basis $\{b'_1, \dots, b'_n\}$ if $b'_i = \omega_{ij} b_j$ holds with $\det(\omega_{ij}) > 0$, and the opposite orientation of \mathcal{V}_n as the basis $\{b'_1, \dots, b'_n\}$ if $b'_i = \omega_{ij} b_j$ holds with $\det(\omega_{ij}) < 0$.

On the page 8 of [2], I have stated that “It is easy to verify that the bases of \mathcal{K}^+ and \mathcal{K}^- are indeed related by an 8×8 diagonal matrix whose determinant is $(-1)^7 < 0$. Consequently, \mathcal{K}^+ and \mathcal{K}^- indeed represent right-oriented and left-oriented vector spaces, respectively, in accordance with our definition of orientation. We can therefore leave the orientation unspecified and write \mathcal{K}^\pm as

$$\mathcal{K}^\lambda = \text{span}\{1, \lambda \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y, \lambda \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_x, \lambda \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z, \lambda \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_\infty, \lambda \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_\infty, \lambda \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_\infty, \lambda I_3 \mathbf{e}_\infty\}, \quad \lambda^2 = 1 \iff \lambda = \pm 1. \quad (\text{R.6})$$

In the later sections in [2], λ is taken as a hidden variable, with real physical consequences for the strong correlations. I do not mean anything different from what I have written in the Subsection 2.3, the title of which is self-explanatory.

Critique: The next problem is with the title and initial remarks of Section 2.4 in the Christian paper. The title is ‘Representation space \mathcal{K}^λ remains closed under multiplication’ and the initial remarks are ‘As an eight-dimensional linear vector space, \mathcal{K}^λ has some remarkable properties. To begin with, \mathcal{K}^λ is closed under multiplication.’ The title and remarks seem odd—we are dealing with the even subset of the Clifford algebra $Cl_{4,0}$ so what is said here follows immediately from this fact. The properties are hardly remarkable per se.

Response: The title of and remarks in the Subsection 2.4 are not odd, especially considering the aim and purpose of the paper. The representation space \mathcal{K}^λ does remain closed under multiplication. And that is indeed a remarkable property for any space, and especially for the space respecting octonion-like non-trivial multiplication rules. In fact, the simpler quaternionic 3-sphere defined in Eq. (2.16) also remains closed under multiplication of any number of quaternions despite the non-trivial rules by which they multiply. If we take, say, one trillion different quaternions from the set (2.16) and multiply them together, *in any order*, then the resulting entity is again a quaternion belonging to the same set. That is quite a remarkable property. The same property holds also for the elements of the set \mathcal{K}^λ .

More importantly, for a locally causal understanding of quantum correlations (which is of course the central goal of the paper), the above property of the sets (2.16) and \mathcal{K}^λ embodies the condition of factorizability demanded by Bell's theorem, as discussed in the appendices A and B of the paper. This is a vital condition for respecting local causality. Therefore stressing the importance of this property in the title and contents of the Subsection 2.4 is quite appropriate.

Critique: More serious is what happens next. It is clear from Christian's Eq. (2.8) that by 'norm' of a general multivector M he means

$$\|M\| = \sqrt{\langle M\tilde{M} \rangle}. \quad (3.6)$$

Response: The left-hand side of the above equation is — by definition — a scalar number, $\|M\|$. There are two equivalent ways to work out this scalar number:

(a) $\|M\|$ = square root of the scalar part $\langle M\tilde{M} \rangle$ of the geometric product $M\tilde{M}$ between M and \tilde{M}

or

(b) $\|M\|$ = square root of the geometric product $M\tilde{M}$ with the non-scalar part of $M\tilde{M}$ set to zero.

The above two definitions of the norm $\|M\|$ are *entirely equivalent*. They give the same scalar value for the norm. Regardless of GA, \tilde{M} is generally said to be the conjugate of M if $M\tilde{M}$ happens to be equal to unity: $M\tilde{M} = 1$.

It is also important to recall that in Geometric Algebra the fundamental product between any two multivectors M and N is the geometric product, MN , *not* the scalar product $\langle MN \rangle$ (or the wedge product $M \wedge N$ for that matter). Therefore, in general, the product that must be used in computing the norm $\|M\|$ that preserves the Clifford algebraic structure of \mathcal{K}^λ is the geometric product $M\tilde{M}$, and not the scalar product $\langle M\tilde{M} \rangle$. To be sure, in practice, if one is interested only in working out the value of the norm $\|M\|$, then it is often convenient to use the definition (a) above. However, when the primary purpose in working out the norm is to preserve the underlying algebraic structure of the space under consideration in a fundamental relation such as

$$\|MN\| = \|M\| \|N\|, \quad (R.7)$$

then the definition of the norm that must be used for that purpose is necessarily the second definition stated above.

In the light of these observations it is not difficult to see that the rest of the critique reproduced below is missing a crucial point. However, for the completeness of my response, let me continue to address the criticism point-by-point.

Critique: We can see that this square root is valid, and won't lead to imaginaries, as follows. Let us set up a general M via defining two 2-spinors ϕ and χ as

$$\begin{aligned} \phi &= a_0 + a_1 e_y e_z + a_2 e_z e_x + a_3 e_x e_y \\ \chi &= b_0 + b_1 e_y e_z + b_2 e_z e_x + b_3 e_x e_y \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

(where the a_μ and b_μ , $\mu = 0, \dots, 3$, are scalars) and write

$$M = \phi + I\chi \quad (3.8)$$

(Note we are going to write I_c as I from now on). Since $I^2 = 1$ we have

$$M\tilde{M} = \phi\tilde{\phi} + \chi\tilde{\chi} + I(\phi\tilde{\chi} + \chi\tilde{\phi}). \quad (3.9)$$

Now, let us define two 4-vectors using the components of ϕ and χ

$$\begin{aligned} a &= a_0 e_\infty + a_1 e_1 + a_2 e_2 + a_3 e_3 \\ b &= b_0 e_\infty + b_1 e_1 + b_2 e_2 + b_3 e_3 \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

(Note we are not saying that ϕ or χ are 4-vectors. We are just defining objects that make it easy to display the components of $M\tilde{M}$.) Then we find $\phi\tilde{\phi} + \chi\tilde{\chi} = a^2 + b^2$ and $\phi\tilde{\chi} + \chi\tilde{\phi}$ is the scalar $2a \cdot b$, meaning

$$M\tilde{M} = a^2 + b^2 + 2a \cdot bI. \quad (3.11)$$

This shows us that $\langle M\tilde{M} \rangle = a^2 + b^2$ is indeed positive if M is non-zero, hence the norm is well-defined.

Response: Despite the intention, this change in notation does not add anything enlightening. In fact, it obscures the physical meanings of the relationship between the spheres S^3 and S^7 that is important in understanding quantum correlations. Moreover, it introduces a subtle form of strawman before knocking it down. The strawman is introduced in the Eq. (3.10) above in the form of the following two arbitrary 4-vectors:

$$\begin{aligned} a &= a_0 e_\infty + a_1 e_1 + a_2 e_2 + a_3 e_3 \\ b &= b_0 e_\infty + b_1 e_1 + b_2 e_2 + b_3 e_3 . \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

Since these vectors are introduced in *ad hoc* manner, nothing prevents us from choosing them so that they remain orthogonal to each other: $a \cdot b = 0$. As we shall see, this already nullifies most of the critique below.

Critique: Given any two general elements X and Y , Christian then decides to normalise them, setting

$$\|X\|^2 = 1, \quad \|Y\|^2 = 1. \quad (3.12)$$

It is not clear why we would wish to do this, but as just established, it is something we can indeed carry out for any non-zero elements.

Response: The motivation for normalizing the general elements X and Y of \mathcal{K}^λ to unity is obvious from the start. It is obvious from the discussions in the abstract, introduction, Section 2, and Figure 2, from which it is clear that we are heading towards a compactified physical space S^3 and its algebraic representation space S^7 , which are well known to be two of the only four parallelizable spheres; namely, S^0 , S^1 , S^3 and S^7 (cf. Appendix A of Ref. [2]).

Critique: So far, so good. However, things go very wrong with equation (2.40). Christian states:

We shall soon see that for vectors X and Y in \mathcal{K}^λ (not necessarily unit) the following relation holds:

$$\|XY\| = \|X\| \|Y\| \quad (2.40).$$

(By ‘vector’ Christian means what we would call ‘multivector’ here, as is clear from the context.) However, this is false.

Response: The validity of Eq. (2.40) of the paper — which is identical to Eq. (2.59) apart from notation — has been explicitly proved in the Royal Society paper and in Ref. [10]. The proof uses the second definition of the norm $\|M\|$:

(b) $\|M\|$ = square root of the geometric product $M\tilde{M}$ with the non-scalar part of $M\tilde{M}$ set to zero.

As I pointed out on page 7, this definition is entirely equivalent to definition (2.8), and it is the correct definition for the norm in the present context, because it preserves the algebraic structure of the space \mathcal{K}^λ within the norm relation (2.40). I have also provided further details of the proof in Ref. [10], which demonstrates that the finite-dimensional algebra \mathcal{K}^λ over the reals can be equipped with a positive definite quadratic form \mathcal{Q} (the square of the norm) such that $\mathcal{Q}(XY) = \mathcal{Q}(X)\mathcal{Q}(Y)$ for all X and Y in \mathcal{K}^λ . Consequently, a product XY would vanish if and only if X or Y vanishes. In other words, \mathcal{K}^λ , equipped with \mathcal{Q} , is a division algebra. Thus, unlike the non-associative octonionic algebra, the 7-sphere I have constructed in [2] corresponds to an *associative* (but of course non-commutative) algebra.

Critique: Consider the quantities

$$I_+ = \frac{1}{2}(1 + I), \quad I_- = \frac{1}{2}(1 - I). \quad (3.13)$$

Since I squares to 1 and is its own reverse, then these satisfy the relations

$$I_+^2 = I_+ \tilde{I}_+ = I_+, \quad I_-^2 = I_- \tilde{I}_- = I_-, \quad I_+ I_- = I_- I_+ = 0. \quad (3.14)$$

We call such quantities ‘idempotents’ (since they square to themselves) and this particular pair are ‘orthogonal’ (since their product is zero). Now let

$$X = \sqrt{2}I_+, \quad Y = \sqrt{2}I_-. \quad (3.15)$$

These satisfy

$$\|X\| = 1, \quad \|Y\| = 1, \quad \text{but} \quad \|XY\| = 0. \quad (3.16)$$

This disproves the assertion in Christian’s (2.40). It also means that the assertion which follows it:

One of the important observations here is that, without loss of generality, we can restrict our representation space to a set of unit vectors in \mathcal{K}^λ

is false, since if $\|X\|$ and $\|Y\|$ are unit vectors, it does *not* follow that $Z = XY$ is also a unit vector, despite what Christian says in his equation (2.41).

Response: Eq. (3.16) in the critique is not valid, because the quantities defined in (3.13) contradict the definition (b) of the norm I have discussed above. It is easy to see using the notation introduced in the critique that the definition (b) of the norm implies that the quantities defined by Eq. (3.16) in the critique [1] amounts to assuming $+1 = -1$.

In the notation of [1], the general element of \mathcal{K}^λ is written as $M = \phi + I\chi$ [see Eq. (3.8) above]. Then, given Eq. (3.9) in the critique and the definition (b) of the norm I discussed above, the normalization condition is given by

$$\phi\tilde{\chi} + \chi\tilde{\phi} = 0 \iff \phi\tilde{\chi} = -\chi\tilde{\phi}. \quad (\text{R.8})$$

Now consider the quantity $I_+ = \frac{1}{2}(1 + I)$ considered in the critique. According to the general element $M = \phi + I\chi$, this quantity is obtained by setting $\phi = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\chi = \frac{1}{2}$. Substituting these values, together with $\tilde{\phi} = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\tilde{\chi} = \frac{1}{2}$ (because $\phi = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\chi = \frac{1}{2}$ are scalars), into the above normalization condition $\phi\tilde{\chi} = -\chi\tilde{\phi}$ leads to the following contradiction:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{2} &= -\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{2} \\ \implies +1 &= -1. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{R.9})$$

Similarly, consider the quantity $I_- = \frac{1}{2}(1 - I)$. According to the general element $M = \phi + I\chi$, this quantity is obtained by setting $\phi = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\chi = -\frac{1}{2}$. Substituting these values, together with $\tilde{\phi} = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\tilde{\chi} = -\frac{1}{2}$ (because $\phi = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\chi = -\frac{1}{2}$ are scalars), into the above normalization condition $\phi\tilde{\chi} = -\chi\tilde{\phi}$ we again arrive at the same contradiction:

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{2} &= +\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{2} \\ \implies -1 &= +1. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{R.10})$$

This proves that the *ad hoc* quantities $I_+ = \frac{1}{2}(1 + I)$ and $I_- = \frac{1}{2}(1 - I)$ confined to a two-dimensional subspace of \mathcal{K}^λ assumed in the critique are not compatible with the normalization condition $\phi\tilde{\chi} + \chi\tilde{\phi} = 0$, and thus they are not compatible with the definition (b) of the norm used to construct the 7-sphere defined in (2.60) or (R.2). In other words, the quantities $I_+ = \frac{1}{2}(1 + I)$ and $I_- = \frac{1}{2}(1 - I)$ are not members of the set (2.60) that constitutes the 7-sphere. Therefore, the claim made in the Eq. (3.16) of the critique is not correct. As a result, the rest of the critique is also nullified. In particular, if X and Y are unit vectors, then so is $Z = XY$, as a consequence of the norm relation (2.40). For further discussion, see the Appendices A and B in Ref. [10].

The above contradictions can be demonstrated more simply by using the constraint

$$f_{\mathcal{K}} = a_0b_0 + a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + a_3b_3 = 0 \quad (\text{R.11})$$

implied by the normalization condition (R.8). Comparing with the general element of \mathcal{K}^λ specified in Eq. (3.8), we can see that in the definitions (3.15) the critique has set the coefficients $a_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $b_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ for X and $a_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $b_0 = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ for Y , with all other coefficients set to zero. Recalling from (3.11) that the norm is of the form $\|M\| = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2 + 2a \cdot bI}$, we first recognize that the only way the norm of X and Y can be scalars as assumed by the critique is by setting $a \cdot b = 0$, which, as we saw above, is equivalent to the constraint (R.11). Substituting the coefficients assumed by the critique in the above constraint we thus immediately arrive at the contradictions $\pm\frac{1}{2} = 0$.

In addition to the above, we can prove more directly that Eq. (3.16) of the critique is not correct. In Eq. (3.15) the multivectors X and Y in \mathcal{K}^λ are constructed by setting $X_0 = Y_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, $X_7 = -Y_7 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, so that it can be written as

$$X = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 + I) \quad \text{and} \quad Y = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1 - I). \quad (\text{R.12})$$

Then (3.14) implies that $\|XY\| = 0$, which can be verified by substituting for the multivectors X and Y from (R.12):

$$\|XY\| = \left\| \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1+I) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1-I) \right\| \quad (\text{R.13})$$

$$= \left\| \frac{1}{2}(1-I^2) \right\| \quad (\text{R.14})$$

$$= \|0\| \quad (\text{R.15})$$

$$= 0, \quad (\text{R.16})$$

where $I^2 = 1$ is used. Next, using $I^\dagger = I$ and $I^2 = 1$, for the right-hand side of the norm relation (R.5) we have

$$\|X\| \|Y\| = \left\| \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1+I) \right\| \left\| \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1-I) \right\| \quad (\text{R.17})$$

$$= \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1+I) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1+I)^\dagger} \right) \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1-I) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1-I)^\dagger} \right) \quad (\text{R.18})$$

$$= \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(1+I)(1+I)} \right) \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(1-I)(1-I)} \right) \quad (\text{R.19})$$

$$= \left(\sqrt{(1+I)} \right) \left(\sqrt{(1-I)} \right) \quad (\text{R.20})$$

$$= \sqrt{(1+I)(1-I)} \quad (\text{R.21})$$

$$= \sqrt{(1-I^2)} \quad (\text{R.22})$$

$$= \sqrt{0} \quad (\text{R.23})$$

$$= 0, \quad (\text{R.24})$$

where we have used geometric products to evaluate the norms. Comparing (R.16) and (R.24) we see that the norm relation $\|XY\| = \|X\| \|Y\|$ is satisfied for the multivectors in (R.12). On the other hand, if we insist on using scalar products for evaluating the norms as done in the critique, then (R.16) remains the same but instead of (R.24) we get

$$\|X\| \|Y\| = \left\| \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1+I) \right\| \left\| \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1-I) \right\| \quad (\text{R.25})$$

$$= \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(1+I) \cdot (1+I)^\dagger} \right) \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(1-I) \cdot (1-I)^\dagger} \right) \quad (\text{R.26})$$

$$= \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(1+I) \cdot (1+I)} \right) \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(1-I) \cdot (1-I)} \right) \quad (\text{R.27})$$

$$= \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(1+1)} \right) \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(1+1)} \right) \quad (\text{R.28})$$

$$= \left(\sqrt{1} \right) \left(\sqrt{1} \right) \quad (\text{R.29})$$

$$= 1, \quad (\text{R.30})$$

which suggests that $\|XY\| \neq \|X\| \|Y\|$, as claimed in the critique. This incompatibility has resulted from the norms evaluated inconsistently in arriving at the contradictory results (R.16) and (R.30). While the product between X and Y for (R.16) is evaluated using the geometric product giving $XY = 0$ so that $\|XY\| = 0$, the norms $\|X\|$ and $\|Y\|$ are evaluated for (R.30) using the scalar products giving $\|X\| = 1$ and $\|Y\| = 1$. But, as demonstrated above, using scalar products to evaluate the norms is inconsistent with the choices made in (R.12) for the coefficients of X and Y .

Critique: In Sect. 2.5 there is a further confusion about a quantity which when first introduced squares to 0, but then later squares to 1. In (2.47) and (2.48) the quantity ε , which satisfies $\varepsilon^2 = 0$ is brought in to allow the definition of *biquaternions*, via

$$\mathbb{Q}_z = \mathbf{q}_r + \mathbf{q}_d \varepsilon \quad (3.17)$$

where \mathbf{q}_r and \mathbf{q}_d are quaternions. In Eq. (2.51), however, ε is identified with $-I$, and it is stated that $\varepsilon^2 = +1$. Thus the previous reference to biquaternions is not correct.

Response: As I explained before, \mathbf{e}_∞ is a null vector in S^3 but a unit vector in the embedding space \mathbb{R}^4 . This is very clearly explained in Subsection 2.1, with Figure 2. In the Eq. (2.51) of Subsection 2.5 it is again made clear, in parenthesis, why $\varepsilon^2 = +1$: “since \mathbf{e}_∞ is a unit vector within \mathcal{K}^λ .” The reference to bi-quaternions in the beginning of the Subsection 2.5 in the Royal Society paper and in Ref. [10] is pedagogical.

Critique: What is actually being introduced is the construction we have used above, where one can write a general element of the even subalgebra of $Cl_{(4,0)}$ as

$$M = \phi + I\chi \quad (3.18)$$

with ϕ and χ as given in Eq. (3.7). We called these 2-spinors above, but it is fine to identify them as quaternions as well. So this shows that translating the quantities introduced by Christian in this section into our notation, we have

$$\mathbf{q}_r = \phi, \quad \mathbf{q}_d = \chi, \quad \mathbb{Q}_z = \mathbf{q}_r + \mathbf{q}_d \varepsilon = M = \phi + I\chi. \quad (3.19)$$

Response: As I noted above, the new notation introduced in the critique does not add anything to the analysis. It ends up obscuring the relationship between S^3 and S^7 that is important for understanding the quantum correlations.

Critique: (A slight problem is that since Christian says that ε is equal to the *reverse* of I and he believes (wrongly) that this is $-I$, some signs will start to get out of drift as regards components of his \mathbf{q}_d quaternion versus our χ , but this does not seem crucial.)

Response: This is not correct. I do not “believe” that $I_4^\dagger = -I_4$. That is quite clear from the multiplication table 1 on page 8. As I have explained above, Eq. (2.25) is an *intermediate step*, important for physical reasons, leading to the correct multiplication table 1 on page 8. There are no “beliefs” in my paper. Every mathematical step in it is presented clearly, explained lucidly, and demonstrated rigorously. In particular, ε is clearly defined as $-\lambda I_3 \mathbf{e}_\infty$ in Eq. (2.51). Ultimately, what is important for the computations is the correctness of the multiplication table 1 given on page 8.

Critique: Now we have so far skipped over one feature of the construction of \mathbb{Q}_z , which is that Christian wants each of \mathbf{q}_r and \mathbf{q}_d to be normalised, with

$$\|\mathbf{q}_r\| = \|\mathbf{q}_d\| = \varrho \quad (3.20)$$

where ϱ is some fixed scalar.

Response: The quaternions \mathbf{q}_r and \mathbf{q}_d are normalized to radius ϱ because they are taken to be elements of the set (2.16) of normalized quaternions. It is unfortunate that the critique seems to have ignored the physical problem being addressed in the paper. But once proper attention is paid to the physical problem being addressed, many mathematical steps taken in the paper become clear without requiring justification at each step. The summary of these steps is stated clearly in the abstract of the paper: “Remarkably, the resulting algebra remains associative, and allows us to understand the origins and strengths of all quantum correlations locally, in terms of the geometry of the compactified physical space, namely, that of a quaternionic 3-sphere, S^3 , with S^7 being its algebraic representation space.” The very mentions of S^3 and S^7 indicate that the quaternions we will be using will have to be normalized.

Critique: He then correctly says in Eq. (2.53) that this means

$$\|\mathbb{Q}_z\| = \sqrt{2}\varrho. \quad (3.21)$$

However, things go very wrong in the next equation. Christian says

Now the normalization of \mathbb{Q}_z in fact necessitates that every \mathbf{q}_r be orthogonal to its dual \mathbf{q}_d

$$\|\mathbb{Q}_z\| = \sqrt{2}\varrho \implies \mathbf{q}_r \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_d + \mathbf{q}_d \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_r = 0. \quad (3.22)$$

This is false. The same result in the above notation [as used in our Eq. (3.11)] would be that

$$\|a\| = \varrho \quad \text{and} \quad \|b\| = \varrho \quad \implies \quad a \cdot b = 0. \quad (3.23)$$

which is patently wrong.

Response: Far from being “patently wrong”, $2a \cdot b \equiv \mathbf{q}_r \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_d + \mathbf{q}_d \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_r = 0$ is the correct normalization condition stemming from the second definition of the norm discussed on the page 7 of this response [the definition (b)] and further explained in Ref. [10]. Unfortunately, as noted before, the change in notation introduced in the critique introduces a subtle form of strawman. The strawman is introduced in the form of the following two arbitrarily chosen 4-vectors:

$$\begin{aligned} a &= a_0 e_\infty + a_1 e_1 + a_2 e_2 + a_3 e_3 \\ b &= b_0 e_\infty + b_1 e_1 + b_2 e_2 + b_3 e_3. \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

Therefore the condition $a \cdot b = 0$ is a strawman and the claim that it is “patently wrong” is a paper tiger. Since these vectors are chosen in *ad hoc* manner, nothing prevents us from choosing them so that they remain orthogonal to each other: $a \cdot b = 0$. That, then, is the condition of normalization equivalent to the condition $\mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0$ in the paper. In terms of the components of \mathbf{q}_r and \mathbf{q}_d , this condition, in turn, is equivalent to the constraint function

$$f_{\mathcal{K}} = -q_0 q_7 + \lambda q_1 q_6 + \lambda q_2 q_5 + \lambda q_3 q_4 = 0, \quad (R.31)$$

which, in the notation introduced in the critique, is identical to

$$f_{\mathcal{K}} = a_0 b_0 + a_1 b_1 + a_2 b_2 + a_3 b_3 = 0. \quad (R.32)$$

This constraint simply reduces the space \mathcal{K}^λ to the sphere S^7 , thereby reducing the 8 dimensions of \mathcal{K}^λ to the 7 dimensions of S^7 , when we use the second definition of the norm discussed on the page 7 of this response. But such a dimensional reduction should not surprise anyone. That is exactly how the normed division algebras work. The sets \mathbb{R} , \mathbb{C} , \mathbb{H} , and \mathbb{O} of dimensions 1, 2, 4, and 8 are reduced to the spheres S^0 , S^1 , S^3 , and S^7 of dimensions 0, 1, 3, and 7, respectively, facilitated by the norm relation $\|XY\| = \|X\| \|Y\|$ and aided by a different constraint function $f = 0$ in each of the four cases. Similarly, in my paper [2] the space \mathcal{K}^λ of 8 dimensions is reduced to the sphere S^7 of 7 dimensions by the above constraint, derived using the geometric product XX^\dagger and the normalization condition $\mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0$, as explained on the page 7 of this response. Thus, nothing unusual is being carried out in my paper in this regard. On the other hand, the 7-sphere thus constructed in the paper has a topology that is different from that of the octonionic S^7 , and that difference is captured by the difference in the corresponding normalization constraints

$$f(q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4, q_5, q_6, q_7) = 0. \quad (R.33)$$

More precisely, the two respective normalization constraints are:

$$f_{\mathcal{O}} = q_0^2 + q_1^2 + q_2^2 + q_3^2 + q_4^2 + q_5^2 + q_6^2 + q_7^2 - \rho^2 = 0, \quad (R.34)$$

which reduces the set \mathbb{O} to the sphere S^7 made up of 8D vectors of fixed length (or radius) ρ , and

$$f_{\mathcal{K}} = -q_0 q_7 + \lambda q_1 q_6 + \lambda q_2 q_5 + \lambda q_3 q_4 = 0, \quad (R.10)$$

which reduces the set \mathcal{K}^λ to the sphere S^7 made up of a different collection of 8D vectors of fixed length (or radius) $\rho = \sqrt{\varrho_r^2 + \varrho_d^2}$. This difference arises because in the paper the fundamental geometric product XX^\dagger is used, as it must be, rather than the non-fundamental scalar product, to derive the constraint $f_{\mathcal{K}} = 0$. But both constraints give an identical result for the values of the norms $\|X\|$, $\|Y\|$, and $\|XY\|$, as I have explained on the page 7 of this response.

Critique: So can we understand why Christian believes this? Tracing through what happens in the following two equations, it is clear that the mistake is made at the point where he says that it is needed for $\mathbb{Q}_z \tilde{\mathbb{Q}}_z$ to be a scalar. If it were needed then indeed it follows that $2a \cdot b = \mathbf{q}_r \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_d + \mathbf{q}_d \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_r$ would have to vanish, but from what has been said about \mathbb{Q}_z so far there is no such requirement—it has just been required that the norm (as defined by Christian and which we examined above) has to have value 2ϱ . It looks as though what is happening is that Christian has temporarily forgotten that the norm is just the scalar part of the product $M\tilde{M}$, not both the scalar and grade-4 parts. This is a very important mistake.

Response: Contrary to the above claim, there is no mistake in the paper [2][10]. I have not forgotten anything, temporarily or otherwise. The norm $\|M\|$ is indeed just the scalar part of the geometric product $M\tilde{M}$. The condition $2a \cdot b = \mathbf{q}_r \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_d + \mathbf{q}_d \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_r = 0$ is a perfectly valid normalization condition, as I have explained in my previous responses.

Critique: Of course we needed a significant mistake, since it is needed to be able to prove the (false) assertion about the product of the norms being the norm of the product. This is repeated in terms of \mathbb{Q} s in Eq. (2.59). The ‘proof’ of this amounts to the fact that if two \mathbb{Q} s each individually have vanishing grade-4 part when forming $\mathbb{Q}_z \tilde{\mathbb{Q}}_z$, then the product of their norms is equal to the norm of their product. This is fine, but only applies to this special class of \mathbb{Q} s, not the whole even subalgebra of $Cl_{(4,0)}$, as Christian claims.

There is a lot of discussion around this part of Sect. 2.5, attempting to say that due to the relations proved for the norms, therefore he has discovered a new *associative* version of the normed division algebra hitherto represented by the octonians, but of course this is false, as it had to be, since the relations he is talking about only apply to a limited subset of the space, not the whole space.

Response: The assertion that the product of the norms is equal to the norm of the product, namely equations (2.40) and (2.59) in the paper, is correct. It has been proved in the paper, and more explicitly in Ref. [10]. See also my previous two responses. In particular, the claim that “This is fine, but only applies to this special class of \mathbb{Q} s, not the whole even subalgebra of $Cl_{(4,0)}$, ...” is not correct, because, as explained above, the dimensional reduction of the eight-dimensional space \mathcal{K}^λ to the 7-dimensional S^7 , aided by the norm relation $\|XY\| = \|X\| \|Y\|$, is precisely how the normed division algebras work. No one should be surprised by such a dimensional reduction in this context.

Critique:

Subsection 3.2. Discussion

This completes a quick survey of the initial problems in the Christian paper, taking us through to the start of the discussion concerning quantum states. Hence this is a good time to set down what the mathematical apparatus Christian has assembled to this point actually amounts to, when stripped of the incorrect results. This can be summarised as follows.

Let us consider the even subalgebra of $Cl_{(4,0)}$ and pick out the elements R from this which satisfy

$$R\tilde{R} = 1$$

i.e. we pick out the set of what are usually called *rotors* in this space. Then Christian’s working to this point boils down to the result that if S is another rotor, then the combination SR is a further rotor, since it satisfies

$$SR(\widetilde{SR}) = SR\tilde{R}\tilde{S} = 1. \quad (3.24)$$

This is for objects which are already normalized to 1. Slightly more generally, if we define $X = \varrho_1 R$ and $Y = \varrho_2 S$, where ϱ_1 and ϱ_2 are scalars, then the relation

$$\|XY\| = \|X\| \|Y\|,$$

which is the basis for Christian’s claims, is true. However, this relation does not apply to all X and Y in \mathcal{K}^λ , but only to an X and Y which are scaled rotors. Of course we knew it could not apply to all of \mathcal{K}^λ since above we gave an explicit counterexample.

Response: In [1] it is written: “However, this relation does not apply to all X and Y in \mathcal{K}^λ , but only to an X and Y which are scaled rotors.” This is a very strange comment. But of course the norm relation $\|XY\| = \|X\| \|Y\|$ only applies to scaled elements of \mathcal{K}^λ . Evidently, by definition, the norm relation involves only *normalized* elements of \mathcal{K}^λ .

Earlier it was wrongly claimed that the normalization condition $2a \cdot b \equiv \mathbf{q}_r \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_d + \mathbf{q}_d \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_r = 0$ that leads to the norm relation $\|XY\| = \|X\| \|Y\|$ is “patently wrong.” But we saw that it is, in fact, the correct normalization condition according to the second definition [definition (b)] of the norm discussed on page 7 of this response, and what is more, both the first and second definitions of the norm give exactly the same scalar number $\|X\|$ for any element $X \in \mathcal{K}^\lambda$.

But now it is claimed that the norm relation $\|XY\| = \|X\| \|Y\|$ is, in fact, trivially true for scaled rotors.

So which is the case? Is my Eq. (2.40) “patently wrong” or trivially true? In fact, it is neither wrong nor trivially true. It is *non-trivially* true. It is instructive to see this in the notation introduced in the Eqs. (3.8) and (3.9) of the critique. In the above comments two *normalized* rotors, R and S , are considered, which can be set up as follows:

$$\|R\| = \sqrt{R\tilde{R}} = \varrho_R \quad (R.35)$$

$$\text{and } \|S\| = \sqrt{S\tilde{S}} = \varrho_S, \quad (R.36)$$

where ϱ_r and ϱ_s are some fixed scalars. Then the product SR of these two rotors is another rotor, giving

$$\|SR\| = \sqrt{(SR)(\widetilde{SR})} \quad (\text{R.37})$$

$$= \sqrt{SR\widetilde{R}\widetilde{S}} \quad (\text{R.38})$$

$$= \sqrt{S\varrho_r^2\widetilde{S}} \quad (\text{R.39})$$

$$= \left(\sqrt{S\widetilde{S}}\right)\varrho_r \quad (\text{R.40})$$

$$= \varrho_s\varrho_r \quad (\text{R.41})$$

$$= \|S\|\|R\|. \quad (\text{R.42})$$

Thus it does appear at first sight that for normalized rotors my Eq. (2.40) is trivially true. But this impression is wrong. Because, in the notation of [1], we have

$$R = \phi + I\chi \quad \text{and} \quad R\widetilde{R} = a^2 + b^2 + 2(a \cdot b)I, \quad (\text{R.43})$$

and analogous relations for S . Thus to normalize R we have to set $a \cdot b = 0$. That is easy enough to do for both R and S , but what is involved in the above derivation is their product SR and its conjugate \widetilde{SR} , and that makes the calculation non-trivial. The non-triviality of the calculation stems from the fact that, unlike the seven imaginaries of octonions, there are only six basis elements of \mathcal{K}^λ that are imaginary. The seventh element, $\lambda I_3 \mathbf{e}_\infty$, squares to $+1$. This is evident from the multiplication table 1 on page 8 of the Royal Society paper. Since the complete proof of the norm relation $\|XY\| = \|X\|\|Y\|$ has been given in Ref. [10], there is no point in my repeating the proof here in the notation of [1].

Thus, contrary to the claim, the results obtained in Section 2 of the paper [2] are quite significant. The main point of Section 2 is physical, as summarized in the abstract: ‘‘Remarkably, the resulting algebra remains associative, and allows us to understand the origins and strengths of all quantum correlations locally, in terms of the geometry of the compactified physical space, namely, that of a quaternionic 3-sphere, S^3 , with S^7 being its algebraic representation space.’’ The mathematics I have discussed in Section 2 of the paper is not only vital for understanding the physical reasons behind the origins and strength of all quantum correlations by means of the interplay between S^3 and S^7 as demonstrated in the later sections, but also necessary for proving that the norm relation (2.40) is *non-trivially* true.

Critique: Now it is a fact that the scaled rotors, while they form a group under composition (basically multiplication from the left), they do not form a group under addition. If we add two of them with some scalar coefficients, then the resulting object when multiplied with its reverse will in general have a grade-4 part, meaning it is no longer a scaled rotor. This kills off any hope that the set of such objects can form a normed division algebra, as claimed.

Response: The fact that scaled rotors do not form a group under addition, and that addition of two rotors in \mathcal{K}^λ when multiplied with its reverse will in general have a grade-4 part, meaning that it will no longer be a scaled rotor, does not prevent \mathcal{K}^λ equipped with the quadratic form $\mathcal{Q}(X)$ from being a normed division algebra. What is involved in the norm relation

$$\|XY\| = \|X\|\|Y\| \quad (\text{2.40})$$

are *normalizable* multivectors X and Y in \mathcal{K}^λ . Consequently, by definition, $\|X\|$ and $\|Y\|$ are purely scalar quantities. And as demonstrated in the Refs. [2] and [10], for normalizable multivectors the grade-4 part of the quantity $\|XY\| = \sqrt{(XY)(XY)^\dagger}$ vanishes identically, thanks to the normalization condition $\mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0$ in the definition of $\mathcal{Q}(X)$.

Critique: We can contrast this in an unambiguous fashion with the situation which operates for S^3 , and its relation to the quaternions. There, if Q is a quaternion (the set of which are just the even subalgebra of $Cl_{3,0}$), then $Q\widetilde{Q}$ automatically has only a scalar part, we do not need to artificially set any other part to 0, and so there is an automatic match to S^3 . As we have seen, this same type of match does not occur for the even subalgebra of $Cl_{4,0}$, since while the scalar part of $X\widetilde{X}$ sets up a nice match with S^7 , the extra constraint from $\langle X\widetilde{X} \rangle_4 = 0$ reduces the overall dimension down to 6, and we are working just with the rotor group.

Response: The first part of this argument is correct, but the last sentence is wrong. It is correct that in the case of scaled quaternions QQ automatically gives a scalar quantity due to cancellation of the bivector parts. On the other hand, in the case of the elements of \mathcal{K}^λ , the additional condition $\mathbf{q}_r \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_d + \mathbf{q}_d \tilde{\mathbf{q}}_r = 0$ is required. But there is nothing artificial about this condition. It derives automatically from the second and equivalent definition of the norm I have employed, as explained above. And it is quite wrong to assert that “the extra constraint from $\langle X \tilde{X} \rangle_4 = 0$ reduces the overall dimension down to 6.” Only the topology of the 7-sphere, not its dimensionality is changed by the constraint

$$f_{\mathcal{K}} = -q_0 q_7 + \lambda q_1 q_6 + \lambda q_2 q_5 + \lambda q_3 q_4 = 0 \quad (\text{R.10})$$

that defines the 7-sphere

$$S^7 = \left\{ \mathbb{Q}_z := \mathbf{q}_r + \mathbf{q}_d \varepsilon \mid \|\mathbb{Q}_z\| = \rho \text{ and } \mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0 \right\}. \quad (\text{R.44})$$

For counting dimensions of S^7 , the above constraint should be compared with the corresponding octonionic constraint

$$f_o = q_0^2 + q_1^2 + q_2^2 + q_3^2 + q_4^2 + q_5^2 + q_6^2 + q_7^2 - \rho^2 = 0, \quad (\text{R.13})$$

which reduces the set \mathbb{O} to the sphere S^7 made out of 8D vectors of fixed length (or radius) ρ . As we can see from the above equations, both constraints involve the same eight variables of the embedding space \mathbb{R}^8 , namely, $q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4, q_5, q_6$, and q_7 , giving the same dimensions for the sphere S^7 of radius ρ , albeit respecting different topologies [21].

Critique: It is necessary to state that none of this is brought out or stated in the Royal Society paper itself. There it categorically states that

$$\|XY\| = \|X\| \|Y\|$$

applies to all of the even subalgebra of $Cl_{4,0}$, which if true would make it a genuine normed division algebra, but of course we have seen that this is mistaken.

Response: In the Royal Society paper [2], the norm relation $\|XY\| = \|X\| \|Y\|$ is proved for all elements of \mathcal{K}^λ using the second definition of the norm [*i.e.*, definition (b)] discussed on the page 7 of this response, which gives identical scalar for the norm $\|X\|$ for any element X in \mathcal{K}^λ . As I demonstrated above, the counterexample in the critique is incompatible with this definition; or, equivalently, incompatible with the normalization condition $\mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0$, because it implies an absurd equality such as $-1 = +1$. Here is the relevant paragraph from the Royal Society paper:

But there is more to the normalization condition $\mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0$ than meets the eye. It also leads to the crucial norm relation (2.40), which is at the very heart of the only possible four normed division algebras associated with the four parallelizable spheres S^0, S^1, S^3 , and S^7 (cf. appendix A). To verify it, consider a product of two different members of the set \mathcal{K}^λ ,

$$\mathbb{Q}_{z1} \mathbb{Q}_{z2} = (\mathbf{q}_{r1} \mathbf{q}_{r2} + \mathbf{q}_{d1} \mathbf{q}_{d2}) + (\mathbf{q}_{r1} \mathbf{q}_{d2} + \mathbf{q}_{d1} \mathbf{q}_{r2}) \varepsilon, \quad (\text{2.57})$$

together with their individual definitions

$$\mathbb{Q}_{z1} = \mathbf{q}_{r1} + \mathbf{q}_{d1} \varepsilon \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{Q}_{z2} = \mathbf{q}_{r2} + \mathbf{q}_{d2} \varepsilon. \quad (\text{2.58})$$

If we now work out the products $\mathbb{Q}_{z1} \mathbb{Q}_{z1}^\dagger$, $\mathbb{Q}_{z2} \mathbb{Q}_{z2}^\dagger$ and $(\mathbb{Q}_{z1} \mathbb{Q}_{z2})(\mathbb{Q}_{z1} \mathbb{Q}_{z2})^\dagger$, then, thanks to the orthogonality condition $\mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0$, the norm relation is not difficult to verify:

$$\|\mathbb{Q}_{z1} \mathbb{Q}_{z2}\| = \|\mathbb{Q}_{z1}\| \|\mathbb{Q}_{z2}\|. \quad (\text{2.59})$$

Without loss of generality we can now restrict our algebraic representation space \mathcal{K}^λ to a unit 7-sphere by setting the radius ρ of S^3 to $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$. In what follows S^7 will provide the conformal (see footnote 1) counterpart of the algebra $Cl_{3,0}$ given in (2.10):

$$\mathcal{K}^\lambda \supset S^7 := \left\{ \mathbb{Q}_z := \mathbf{q}_r + \mathbf{q}_d \varepsilon \mid \|\mathbb{Q}_z\| = 1 \text{ and } \mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0 \right\}, \quad (\text{2.60})$$

where $\varepsilon = -\lambda I_3 \mathbf{e}_\infty$, $\varepsilon^2 = \mathbf{e}_\infty^2 = +1$,

$$\mathbf{q}_r = q_0 + q_1 \lambda \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y + q_2 \lambda \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_x + q_3 \lambda \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z, \text{ and } \mathbf{q}_d = -q_7 + q_6 \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y + q_5 \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_x + q_4 \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z, \quad (\text{2.61})$$

so that

$$\mathbb{Q}_z = q_0 + q_1 \lambda \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_y + q_2 \lambda \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_x + q_3 \lambda \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_z + q_4 \lambda \mathbf{e}_x \mathbf{e}_\infty + q_5 \lambda \mathbf{e}_y \mathbf{e}_\infty + q_6 \lambda \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{e}_\infty + q_7 \lambda I_3 \mathbf{e}_\infty. \quad (\text{2.62})$$

Admittedly, a detailed proof of Eq. (2.59) is not included in the Royal Society paper because the focus of the paper is elsewhere. But, as we can see from the above quotation, sufficient information is provided in the paper so that a proof of Eq. (2.59) can be worked out. Moreover, a detailed and explicit proof of Eq. (2.59) is now available in Ref. [10]. See, especially, Appendix B of that paper.

Critique: Thus Sects. 1 and 2 of the paper succeed only in showing that the set of rotors of $Cl_{4,0}$ (i.e. even elements of $Cl_{4,0}$ which satisfy $MM = 1$) are closed under multiplication. This is a trivial result which can be established in only a few lines. All the associated statements about normed division algebras, oriented bases, Hopf fibrations, S^7 , E_8 etc. appear to be irrelevant and not substantiated by what is shown in the paper. Moreover, the paper itself gives no inkling that the restriction to rotors is being applied and indeed stresses the applicability of crucial formulae, such as (2.40), to *all* members of $Cl_{4,0}$, which is unfortunately false.

Response: I disagree with the above comments. From my previous comments it should be evident why I disagree. What I have demonstrated in Section 2.4 of the Royal Society paper [2] is that the representation space \mathcal{K}^λ defined in

$$\mathcal{K}^\lambda \supset S^7 := \left\{ Q_z := \mathbf{q}_r + \mathbf{q}_d \varepsilon \mid \|Q_z\| = 1 \text{ and } \mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0 \right\}, \quad (\text{R.60})$$

with or without the normalization $\|Q_z\| = 1$ and the constraint $\mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0$, remains closed under multiplication. Moreover, I have shown that the Hopf fibrations of S^3 and S^7 are absolutely essential for understanding the origins and strengths of quantum correlations. These concepts are discussed in considerable detail, with figures, in the Royal Society paper [2]. In particular, I have demonstrated in my comments above that the claim that “the paper itself gives no inkling that the restriction to rotors is being applied and indeed stresses the applicability of crucial formulae, such as (2.40), to *all* members of $Cl_{4,0}$, which is unfortunately false” has no mathematically justifiable basis.

Critique: It is of course possible that all Christian needs in the second part of the paper, beginning Sect. 3, is the reduced result concerning scaled rotors that has just been described, but this would need a separate development with some quite different mathematics than actually given in the paper.

Response: The mathematics and physics presented in my Royal Society paper [2] are quite adequately developed. There is no need for a separate development with different mathematics than what is developed and presented in the paper.

Recall that in the proof of the norm relations (2.59) we assumed the normalization condition $\mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0$. But the composition law holds in general for the algebra \mathcal{K}^λ even without assuming this special condition. As I have shown in Appendix B of Ref. [10], the norm relation (2.59) can be obtained as a special case of the general composition law. The geometric product $Q_z Q_z^\dagger$ between the general element Q_z in \mathcal{K}^λ and its conjugate Q_z^\dagger is of the general form

$$Q_z Q_z^\dagger = (\text{a scalar}) + (\text{a scalar}) \times \varepsilon, \quad (\text{R.45})$$

with $\varepsilon^2 = +1$. Thus, the square of the norm resembles a split complex number [22] rather than a real scalar. However, as I have proved in Appendix B of Ref. [10], the composition law continues to hold for the algebra \mathcal{K}^λ in general:

$$\|Q_{z1} Q_{z2}\|^2 = \|Q_{z1}\|^2 \|Q_{z2}\|^2. \quad (\text{R.46})$$

In other words, the algebra \mathcal{K}^λ is a normed division algebra even without assuming the condition $\mathbf{q}_r \mathbf{q}_d^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_d \mathbf{q}_r^\dagger = 0$, or, equivalently, without assuming that $Q_z Q_z^\dagger$ in (R.45) is a scalar. On the other hand, if we set $\mathbf{q}_{r1} \mathbf{q}_{d1}^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_{d1} \mathbf{q}_{r1}^\dagger = 0$ and $\mathbf{q}_{r2} \mathbf{q}_{d2}^\dagger + \mathbf{q}_{d2} \mathbf{q}_{r2}^\dagger = 0$ as it is done in proving the norm relation (2.59) in Ref. [2], then the above composition law reduces to the norm relation (2.59):

$$\|Q_{z1} Q_{z2}\| = \sqrt{\varrho_{r1}^2 \varrho_{r2}^2 + \varrho_{r1}^2 \varrho_{d2}^2 + \varrho_{d1}^2 \varrho_{r2}^2 + \varrho_{d1}^2 \varrho_{d2}^2} = \|Q_{z1}\| \|Q_{z2}\|. \quad (\text{R.47})$$

The advantage of this special case is that it reduces the norms from a split complex form to purely scalar quantities. For the proof of (R.46) and (R.47) and for further details, see Appendix B of Ref. [10].

III. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper I have addressed a large number of incorrect claims made in the critique [1] against the geometrical 7-sphere framework I have presented in [2] and [23], and demonstrated that none of the claims made in the critique are valid objections to the 7-sphere framework. In [23], I have also addressed similar claims made by the same author.

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